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EFFECT OF GRINDING ON SOME MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF OSUN STATE CERAMIC TILES

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Ceramic is an engineering material that has endeared itself to many sectors especially the building services sector where it is used for floor tiles. Machining is a necessary finishing operation after casting and other forming operations. A very important machining operation performed on ceramic materials such as tiles is grinding to pave way for easy installation, aesthetics and safety. This work investigates the elemental and chemical composition of the raw materials used in the production of the ceramic tiles under investigation and study the effect of different grinding procedures on some mechanical properties of the ceramic tiles. The tiles were ground at two different grinding speeds and two different levels (continuous and intermittent at 2 seconds intervals). Breaking strength, flexural strength, hardness, and surface roughness before and after grinding were analyzed using the Signal-to-Noise (S/N) ratio. The result revealed that the elements and their respective oxides present in the raw materials were able to give strength, rigidity and support to the ceramic article. Also, grinding was found to affect the mechanical properties of the ceramic tile samples as the breaking strength and flexural strength reduces from 339.77 N for the control sample to as low as 273.30 N and 16.40 N/mm² respectively.

Keywords: ceramic tiles, grinding, breaking strength, flexural strength, hardness

1. Introduction

Ceramic tiles are extremely vitrified clay-based, materials that are usually produced from triaxial blends of kaolin ($\text{Al}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_5(\text{OH})_4$), quartz (SiO_2), and feldspar ($\text{K, Na, Ca}_2\text{O. Al}_2\text{O}_3. 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) [1-3]. It is a hygiene product primarily produced from a porous body and usually with a coating of white or colored glaze [4]. It is one of the most important products used in the construction sector [5-6]. For hundreds of years, ceramic tile has been used to beautify bathrooms, living rooms, kitchens, laboratories, medical centers, shopping malls, public conveniences, and schools) and the clad exterior walls of buildings [4-7].

Machining is a manufacturing approach that is used to steadily remove excess materials from an article to produce the desired shape, dimension, and surface finish using different cutting methods [8]. Machining operations which usually include grinding, milling, drilling, turning, etc. are mostly carried out on metal and other engineering materials. For instance, Iseri *et al.* [9] machined zirconia ceramic using a custom-made grinding apparatus with different grinding procedures and found out that different grinding procedures had a counteracting effect on the flexural strength of zirconia. Meanwhile, Krajcarza *et al.* [10] evaluated the ability of abrasive water-jet traverse to cut ceramic tiles. The study focused on determining the effectiveness of abrasive water-jet traverse speed on the kerf width of ceramic tiles to be cut and found that the ceramic tiles' kerf width was slightly narrower at the bottom with several micrometers difference.

According to the European Commission [11], it may be necessary to subject ceramic tiles to machining operations while the final geometry or dimensional tolerance of the tiles cannot be achieved technically or with sufficient accuracy during the primary production process. Ceramic bodies are difficult to machine and therefore break abruptly or are damaged during machining operation or functional loading [9, 12-14].

The installation of ceramic tile usually requires cutting and/or grinding [15]. After installation, however, drilling of the tiles on the walls and floors is frequently required for Mechanical and Electrical (M&E) service providers to fix cabinets, sanitary wares, sockets, accessories, etc. While grinding of edges is necessary to ensure quality edge finish after cutting and hazard elimination in order to promote safety. The European Commission [11] also align with machining operation like sawing and grinding as requirements for the installation of wall and floor tiles on buildings; and drilling, to facilitate the installation of sanitary fixtures and accessories.

Meanwhile, several studies have demonstrated that the mechanical properties of ceramic tiles are germane to the performance of tiles after installation [4, 13, 16]. Flexural strength of ceramics is an important property for all applications involving impact loading conditions [4, 9, 13, 16-17], with tiles falling into that category due to various machining operations carried out on it before and after installation. The limits of breaking strength and flexural strength of any specimen are determined by both water absorption and thickness

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Table 1

Ceramic tile samples produced for grinding operation

Runs	Test sample	Dimension (mm)	Designation
1	Flexural strength (Machined)	140 x 45 x 8	R
2	Flexural strength (Control)	140 x 45 x 5	Rc
3	Breaking strength (Machined)	140 x 45 x 8	S
4	Breaking strength (Control)	140 x 45 x 5	Sc
5	Hardness (Machined)	10 x 10 x 10	H
6	Hardness (Control)	10 x 10 x 7	Hc

Table 2

Taguchi's Approach to Design Applied to the Grinding Experiments

Symbol	Factors	Unit	Levels	
			Continues Grinding (CG)	Intermittent Grinding (IG)
X ₁	High Speed (HS)	Rev/min	HS	LS
X ₂	Low Speed (LS)	Rev/min	LS	LS

HS – High speed, LS – Low speed, CG – Continuous grinding, IG – Intermittent grinding

of the specimen and it depends on the body composition, dimensions, and morphology of the flaws [4]. The flexural strength represents the highest stress experienced within the material at the point of failure. Ceramic systems are materials usually of low modulus of rupture [18].

Iseri *et al.* [9] showed that the flexural strength of zirconia ceramic is greatly affected by grinding, while the machinability of ceramic materials affects its hardness and strength [19] which in turn is affected by the properties of raw materials used in the production of ceramic tiles [3]. Consequently, the work seeks to characterize the raw materials used in the local production of the ceramic tiles and investigate the effect of different grinding procedures on some mechanical properties of ceramic tiles, since grinding is the most common machining process employed during the installation of tiles.

2. Materials and Methodology

Locally produced ceramic tiles manufactured from clay collected from Ipetumodu, an area in Ife North Local Government of Osun State; silica sand collected from the Isasa River, the boundary between the Ayedaade and Ife North Local Government areas of Osun State; and feldspar collected from Osogbo, the capital of Osun State, all in Nigeria was used for the production of ceramic tiles [20]. NEC 5SDH 1.5 MV Pelletron Accelerator (Model: 5SDH with an accuracy of 0.0001%) was used characterized the three locally sourced raw materials as described Abiola *et al.* [21]. As shown in Table 1, three replicates of ceramic samples run 1, 3, and 5 were produced for flexural strength, breaking strength, and hardness test respectively after grinding. A mini variable speed bench grinding machine (model LYZ3MM manufactured by A1Indusworld) was used to grind the ceramic tiles. The knob of the grinding machine was adjusted until an actual grinding speed of 500 rpm for low-speed and 2600 for high-speed was achieved as verified

by a Tachometer. The specimen was marked 3 mm away from one side and ground until a 3 mm reduction of the specimen was achieved with continuous grinding (CG), and 2 seconds of intermittent grinding (IG) respectively. Control specimen was also analyzed but without grinding as described by Iseri *et al.* [9]. The Four runs (L-4) of grinding experiments used in the study are shown in Table 2. Flexural strength, breaking strength, hardness, and surface roughness of the specimens were determined as responses for each run of the experiment and taken as dependent variables.

The averages roughness (Ra) of the surface of machined specimens after the grinding operation was measured using a digital surface roughness gauge with piezoelectric pick up (Model: SRT-6223+) as shown in Fig. 1. The measurement was repeated four times as described by Omidiji *et al.* [22] and the average readings were recorded and presented.

Fig. 1 - Digital surface roughness gauge used for the experiment

2.1. Determination of Signal to Noise Ratio

The term signal represents the desired value and noise represents the possible error [23]. Signal to Noise (S/N) ratio cut off unwanted interference that may have happened in the cause of running the experiments. Taguchi's method was used to identify the optimum cutting parameter levels to minimize the surface roughness. A Low

surface roughness value will be desirable for maintaining higher tile quality; therefore, the smaller, which is the better, Signal to Noise ratio was used and can be calculated using equation 1.

$$\frac{S}{N} = -10 \log \left\{ \frac{1}{r} \sum_{i=1}^r Ra_i^2 \right\} \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, r, \quad (1)$$

where Ra_i is the value of surface roughness for the i th run in r replications [22].

2.2. Mechanical Properties Test

After the machining operation, the different ceramic samples were subjected to breaking strength and flexural strength using the Universal Strength Testing Machine (Serial No.: 140535, manufactured by Okhard Machine Tools Ltd); while the hardness test was investigated using Mohr’s hardness test method in line with [2].

The breaking strength was calculated from equation (2) as:

$$S = \frac{FL}{b} \quad (2)$$

where, S is the breaking strength, in Newton; F is the breaking load, in Newton; L is the distance between the supporting rods, in millimeters (65 mm); b is the width of the test specimen, in millimeters as shown in Figure 2.

From the same test (Figure 2), the modulus of rupture also known as flexural strength was calculated for each sample of ceramic tiles using equation (3).

$$R = \frac{3S}{2h^2} \quad (3)$$

where R is the modulus of rupture, in N/mm^2 ; S is the breaking strength or force, in Newton; h is the minimum thickness of the test tile specimen, in millimeters.

Fig. 2 - Placement of specimen on Universal Strength Testing Machine for breaking strength and flexural strength test

3.Results and Discussion

3.1. Composition of the Raw Materials

The results presented in Table 3 shows the elemental as well as the chemical composition of the clay, silica-sand and feldspar raw materials used in the production of the ceramic tile samples investigated in this study. The result shows

that the raw materials (clay, silica-sand and feldspar) has high silicon (Si) content 64.9135%, 93.7597%, and 61.0271%; and its oxide (SiO_2), 71.3165%, 95.2810%, and 68.8503% respectively. The clay sample is of the illitic-kaolinitic type and has a sizably high silicon concentration as described by Vasic et al. [5]. The clay used to make the ceramic tiles samples gives fluidity or plasticity to the ceramic product during the forming process [23]. Additionally, a high silicon content in the raw materials helps to lessen the tendency of the ceramic body to warp or deform at high temperature, as well as provide support, control shrinkage, improve density, hardness and rigidity in ceramic products [4, 21].

The next predominant element in the raw materials (clay, silica-sand and feldspar) is Aluminum (Al) with 16.5986%, 1.9904% and 16.1590% and its oxide 16.1062%, 1.7865% and 16.1015% respectively. The ceramic tiles made from these raw materials, can safely be referred to as silicon-aluminate materials [5, 25-26] because of the predominance of silicon and aluminum, as well as their oxides. The increase in aluminum oxide among the other oxides in the clay can help to provide plasticity [4], and the formation of mullite fibers at high temperature can help to improve the flexural strength of ceramic samples [24]. The reduced silicon and increase aluminum and their oxide as well as the large amount of potassium oxide (K_2O) and Sodium oxide (Na_2O) in the feldspar compare to the other materials help to guarantee the effectiveness of the feldspar as good fluxing agent by forming a glassy phase at lower sintering temperature during the firing operation [27-28].

3.2. Implication of Grinding

Table 4 shows the effect of grinding on the mechanical properties of the ceramic tile samples. The grinding was carried out at low speed (500 rpm) and high speed (2600 rpm) and monitored with a tachometer. Based on the result, the control (unground sample) is the strongest on the bases of its best average breaking strength, 339.77 N; flexural strength, 20.39 N/mm^2 ; and Mohr’s hardness, 4 MH recorded. Apart from the control sample, samples ground continuously at high-speed have higher ground average breaking strength, flexural strength, and Mohr’s hardness (319.09 N, 19.15 N/mm^2 , and 3.5 MH) compare to samples ground intermittently at high speed (296.93 N, 17.82 N/mm^2 , and 3.5 MH) respectively. At the low speed and with continuous grinding, the average breaking strength, flexural strength, and Mohr’s hardness were 299.89 N, 17.99 N/mm^2 , and 4 MH respectively; corresponding values for samples ground intermittently at low speed were 273.30 N, 16.40 N/mm^2 , and 4 MH respectively. Comparing the test specimens, sample ground continuously at

Table 3

Chemical composition of the raw materials used in the production of the ceramic tile samples"

Periodic Number	Element	Oxide	Element. Value (%)			Oxide Value (%)		
			Clay	Silica Sand	Feldspar	Clay	Silica Sand	Feldspar
11	Na	Na ₂ O	1.3722	0.6625	5.7406	0.9499	0.4243	4.0807
12	Mg	MgO	1.1410	0.1516	0.0700	0.9715	0.1195	0.0612
13	Al	Al ₂ O ₃	16.5986	1.9904	16.1590	16.1062	1.7865	16.1015
14	Si	SiO ₂	64.9135	93.7597	61.0271	71.3165	95.2810	68.8503
15	P	P ₂ O ₅	-	0.1026	0.1689	-	0.1117	0.2043
17	Cl	Cl	1.1297	0.0137	0.2110	0.5802	0.0065	0.1113
19	K	K ₂ O	7.3946	0.7230	16.3283	4.5743	0.4138	10.3726
20	Ca	CaO	1.4020	0.3493	-	1.0075	0.2322	-
22	Ti	TiO ₂	0.5978	0.9767	0.0495	0.5119	0.7739	0.0436
23	V	V ₂ O ₃	0.0272	-	-	0.0205	-	-
24	Cr	Cr ₂ O ₃	0.0305	-	-	0.0229	-	-
25	Mn	MnO	0.0370	0.0337	0.0032	0.0245	0.0207	0.0022
26	Fe	Fe ₂ O ₃	5.1591	1.1639	0.1837	3.7882	0.7904	0.1385
28	Ni	NiO	-	0.0036	-	-	0.0021	-
29	Cu	Cu ₂ O	-	0.0414	-	-	0.0221	-
30	Zn	ZnO	0.0018	0.0107	-	0.0011	0.0063	-
35	Br	Br	-	0.0061	0.0013	-	0.0029	0.0007
37	Rb	Rb ₂ O	0.0016	0.0021	0.0574	0.0009	0.0011	0.0332
38	Sr	SrO	0.0902	0.0090	-	0.0548	0.0051	-
40	Zr	ZrO ₂	0.0832	-	-	0.0577	-	-
56	Ba	BaO	0.0202	-	-	0.0116	-	-

Table 4

Mechanical Properties of Grinding Experiments

Runs	Factor level		Responses				
	X ₁	X ₂	Ra (µm)	S/N ratio	Breaking strength (N)	Flexural strength (N/mm ²)	Mohr's hardness (MH)
Control			62.92	-51.21	339.77	20.39	4
1	HS	CG	71.96	-52.37	319.09	19.15	3.5
2	HS	IG	89.02	-54.22	296.93	17.82	3.5
3	LS	CG	91.27	-54.44	299.89	17.99	4
4	LS	IG	122.26	-56.97	273.30	16.40	4

Ra – Surface roughness; S/N ratio – Signal-to-Noise ration; HS – High speed; LS – Low speed; CG – Continuous grinding; IG – Intermittent grinding

high speed resulted in the highest strength level while specimen ground intermittently at low speed had the lowest strength values.

In this study, the effect of low and high-speed grinding on the mechanical properties of ceramic tiles was compared. The influence of the grinding period (continuous and intermittent grinding) was also evaluated. It was shown that all the different grinding procedures adopted had a contradictory effect on the mechanical properties of ceramic tiles. Table 4 reveals that the flexural strength of the ceramic tile reduces with increased hardness. This was corroborated by Callister [29], who showed that the hardness of any material is inversely proportional to its ductility and that a ductile material withstands higher strain before it ruptures. A brittle material tends to rupture with little strain, the reason for the sample ground at low speed to have higher mohr's hardness and lower breaking and flexural strength.

The specimens ground continuously with low speed had 9.7% higher strength than those ground intermittently while specimens ground continuously with high speed had 7.5% higher strength than

those ground intermittently. However, the control sample had 24.3% higher strength than intermittent grinding with low-speed, 12.8% higher strength than continuous grinding with low-speed, 14.4% higher strength than intermittent grinding with high speed, and 6.5% higher strength than continuous grinding with high speed.

Based on the results, it was revealed that grinding procedures had an negative effect on the mechanical properties of the ceramic tiles produced locally which is in agreement with Quinn *et al.* [30]. Intermittent grinding which can be considered as rough grinding, may be responsible for the low strength recorded with intermittent grinding and this is due to residual crack caused by repeated impact with the grinding wheel as described by Wang *et al.* [31]. As the strength of ceramic tiles is known to be affected by a crack [32]; the repeated impact of the grinding machine on the ceramic tiles sample due to intermittent grinding could result in the possible crack(s) which affect the strength of samples ground intermittently. While the higher strength recorded with continuous grinding compared to intermittent grinding may be due to continuous and

increased heat generation associated with continuous grinding Iseri *et al.* [9]. It is expected that the higher temperature resulting from continuous grinding could alter the microstructure and crystalline condition of the ceramic sample. Thus, the higher strength with samples ground continuously.

Fig. 3 - Surface roughness of ceramic sample machines using different grinding procedures

Figure 3 shows the comparison between the surface roughness of the different ceramic samples before and after grinding. The surface roughness of the control sample of 62.92 µm and S/N ratio of -51.21 is found to be better when compared to the 71.96 µm and -52.37 for sample grind continuously with high-speed; 89.02 µm and -54.22 for sample grind intermittently with high-speed; 91.27 µm and -54.44 for sample grind continuously with low-speed, and 122.26 µm and 56.97 for sample grind intermittently with low-speed respectively.

Considering the low surface roughness and high Mohr's hardness of the control sample compared to the machined sample, it is convenient to assume that the fluxes developed as a result of the molten feldspar as the ceramic attained its sintering temperature during production have covered the surfaces of the ceramic sample and close all the pores within the ceramic article. Thereby, increasing the hardness in improving the smoothness of the control ceramic sample [20, 26, 33].

It should be noted that scatter obtained in the continuous grinding process is always slightly less compared to the intermittent grinding process. This may be due to mechanical shocks or repeated impact load generated by the intermittent grinding process [34].

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, the raw materials used in this study possesses quality amount of silicon mineral which help to support the rigidity, strength, hardness and control shrinkage in the ceramic tiles. Also, the aluminum, potassium and sodium in the feldspar

material help generate enough flux needed to form glassy phase on ceramic articles.

Furthermore, all grinding procedures had a damaging effect on the mechanical properties of the ceramic tile samples. The best ceramic grinding procedure was achieved with continuous grinding at high speed which revealed breaking strength, flexural strength, and surface roughness of 319.09 N, 19.15 N/mm², 3.5 MH, and 71.96 µm respectively.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. J. Souza, B. C. A. Pinheiro & J. N. F. Holanda, Processing of Floor Tiles Bearing Ornamental Rock-Cutting Waste, *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, 2010, **210**, 1898–1904.
- [2] O. Abiola, A. Oke, B. Omidiji & D. Adetan, Effect of Firing Temperature on some Mechanical Properties of Osun State Ceramic Tile, *East African Journal of Engineering*, 2021, **4** (1), 13-21.
- [3] E. Rat, S. Martínez-Martínez, J. A. Sanchez-Garrido, L. P´erez-Villarejo, E. Garzon & P. J. Sanchez-Soto, Characterization, Thermal and Ceramic Properties of Clays from Alhabia (Almería, Spain), *Ceramics International*, 2023, **49**, 14814–14825
- [4] H. A. El Nouhy, Assessment of some Locally Produced Egyptian Ceramic Wall Tiles, *Housing and Building National Research Center Journal*, 2013, **9**, 201–209.
- [5] M. V. Vasic, L. Pezo, M. R. Vasic, N. Mijatovic, M. Mitric & Z. Radojevic, What is the most Relevant Method for Water Absorption Determination in Ceramic Tiles Produced by Illitic-Kaolinitic Clays? The Mystery Behind the Gresification Diagram, *Boletin De La Sociedad Espanola De Ceramica Vidrio*, 2022, **61**, 241–251.
- [6] B. Ngayakamo, A. Bello & A. P. Onwualu, Valorization of Granite Waste Powder as a Secondary Flux Material for Sustainable Production of Ceramic Tiles, *Cleaner Materials*, 2022, **4** (100055), 1-8
- [7] R. P. Goldberg, The Effects and Control of Moisture in Ceramic Tile Facades, *Castellon*, 2021, **94**, 231-247.
- [8] O. Khayal, In Design for Machining, 2019. Available from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/334282701_DESIGN_FOR_MACHINING. (Accessed June 17, 2019)
- [9] U. Iseri, Z. Ozkurt, E. Kazazoglu & D. Kucukoglu, Influence of Grinding Procedures on the Flexural Strength of Zirconia Ceramics, *Brazilian Dental Journal*, 2010, **21**(6), 528-532.
- [10] D. Krajcarza, D. Bańkowska & P. Młynarczyk, The Effect of Traverse Speed on Kerf Width in AWJ Cutting of Ceramic Tiles, *TRANSCOM 2017: International scientific conference on sustainable, modern and safe transport. Procedia Engineering*, 2017, **192**, 469–473.
- [11] European Commission, In Reference Document on Best Available Techniques in the Ceramic Manufacturing Industry, 2019. Available from <http://eippcb.jrc.es>. (Accessed November 9, 2019)
- [12] T. Kato, K. Ohashi, M. Fuji & M. Takahashi, Water Absorption and Retention of Porous Ceramics Fabricated by Waste Resources, *Journal of Ceramic Society of Japan*, 2008, **116**, (2), 212-215.

- [13] A. Mijoska, E. Bajraktarova-Valjakova, V. Stevkoska-Korunovska, N. Gigovski, B. Kapusevska & J. Bajevska, Flexure Strength of Zirconia Veneering Ceramics, *Journal of Dental and Medical Sciences*, 2016, **15** (1), 85-88.
- [14] E. Jalalian & N. S. Aletaha, The Effect of Two Marginal Designs (Chamfer and Shoulder) on the Fracture Resistance of all Ceramic Restorations, *Inceram: An in Vitro Study*, *Journal of Prosthodontic Research*, 2011, **55**, 121–125.
- [15] J. M. Framinan, R. Leisten & R. Ruiz, A Case Study: Ceramic Tiles Production. In J.M. Framinan, R. Leisten and R. Ruiz Garcia (eds). *Manufacturing Scheduling Systems*. London: Springer, 2014, 371-395.
- [16] A. Belenky & D. Rittel, Static and Dynamic Flexural Strength of 99.5% Alumina: Relation to Surface Roughness, *Mechanics of Materials*, 2012, **54**, 91–99.
- [17] E. K. Alege & T. S. Alege, Selected Clays of the Bida and Anambra Basins of Nigeria: Their Characteristics, Fired Properties and Ceramic-Suitability, *International Journal of Science and Technology*, 2013, **2** (7), 560–567.
- [18] M. F. Ashby, *Materials Selection in Mechanical Design*, 3rd ed. Pergamon Press, Butterworth-Heinemann Linacre House, Jordan Hill, Oxford, 2005.
- [19] M. P. Groover, *Fundamentals of Modern Manufacturing: Materials, Processes, and Systems*. 5th ed. John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2013, 224-225.
- [20] O. Abiola, A. Oke, B. Omidiji & D. Adetan, Effect of Raw Materials on some Physical Properties of Osun State Ceramic Tile, *Journal of Engineering Studies and Research*, 2021, **27** (1), 7-12.
- [21] O. Abiola, A. Oke, B. Omidiji & D. Adetan, The Effect of Beneficiation on some Properties of Osun State Ceramic Raw Materials, *Journal of Casting & Materials Engineering*, 2019, **3** (3), 62-66.
B. V. Omidiji, H. A. Owolabi, T. A. Morakinyo & A. Olukoga, Effect of Machining Parameters on the Surface Roughness of Al-Si alloy, *FUTA Journal of Engineering and Engineering Technology*, 2015, **9** (2), 103-108.
- [22] J. L. Bombazaro & A. M. Bernardin, Improving plasticity of kaolins by high-energy milling for use in porcelain tile compositions, *Open Ceramics*, 2022, **10** (100256), 1-11.
- [23] D. Deepak & D. Anjaiah, Effect of Process Parameters on the Surface Roughness Produced during Machining of Ceramics using AWSJ: An experimental Investigation by Taguchi Signal to Noise Ratio. *WJTA-IMCA Conference and Expo* (October 25-27, 2017), New Orleans, Louisiana, 2017, 2-9.
- [24] W. Ochen, F. M. D'ujanga, B. Oruru & P. W. Olupot, Physical and mechanical properties of porcelain tiles made from raw materials in Uganda, *Results in Materials*, 2021, **11** (100195), 1-6.
- [25] Y. Et-Tayea, A. Harrati, A. Rachid, H. Nasri, A. Attou, Y. Arkame, A. Manni, Y. Mamouch, A. El Bouari, F. El Khazanti & C. Sadik, Mineralogical and Physico-Chemical Characterization of Bentonite Materials from the Oued Zemmour Area (Oriental Rif, Nador-Morocco): Valorization in Ceramic Field, *Boletin De La Sociedad Espanola De Ceramica Vidrio*, 2022, **334**, 1–16.
- [26] K. Kayaci, The use of perlite as flux in the production of porcelain stoneware tiles, *Boletin De La Sociedad Espanola De Ceramica Vidrio*, 2021, **60**, 283–290.
- [27] V. Fuertes, J. J. Reinoso, J. F. Fernandez & E. Enríquez, Engineered Feldspar-Based Ceramics: A Review of their Potential in Ceramic Industry, *Journal of the European Ceramic Society*, 2022, **42**, 307–326.
- [28] W. D. Cllister, *Fundamentals of Materials Science and Engineering*, 5th ed. John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2001.
- [29] G. D. Quinn, L. K. Ives & S. Jahanmir, *Machining Damage Cracks: How to Find and Characterize them by Fractography*, *Ceramic Engineering and Science Proceedings*, 2003, **24**, 383-394.
- [30] C. Y. Wang, X. Wei & H. Yuan, *Materials and Manufacturing Processes*, AMP, 2002, **17** (3), 403-413.
- [31] K. Mohd, and M. Hasmaliza, "Effect of Rutile on Modulus of Rupture in Ceramic Glaze," 5th International Conference on Recent Advances in Materials, Minerals and Environment (RAMM) & 2nd International Postgraduate Conference on Materials, Mineral and Polymer (MAMIP), 4-6 August 2015. *Procedia Chemistry*, 2016, **19**, 10–14.
- [32] A. M. Tullu, T. T. Terfasa, E. A. Zerfe, M. Tadese, E. Beyene, A. M. Abebe & D. M. Adoshe, Effect of Cullet on Firing Temperature and dielectric properties of porcelain insulator, *Heliyon*, 2022, **8**, 1-6.
- [33] T. Tawakoli & B. Azarthoushang, Intermittent Grinding of Advanced Ceramic with the T-Tool Grinding Wheel, *Advanced Materials Research*, DOI: 10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMR, 2010,126-128.
